

Milligram Determination of some Compounds of Anthracene Oil Fraction of Coal Tar

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The reported methods¹ of estimation of polynuclear hydrocarbons in anthracene oil are not suitable on milligram scale. Later on several instrumental techniques² have also been developed. A titrimetric method for the milligram estimation of some of the compounds in anthracene oil using the oxidant $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ reagent³ is described here. Fluoranthene consumes 6 moles of the Fe^{III} reagent and gives fluoranthenequinone as the product. To establish the mechanism of oxidation, fluoranthene (0.5 g) was treated with excess of the reagent for 20 min. After completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was cooled in an ice-bath for 25-30 min and the brownish precipitate was filtered, extracted and dried (m.p. 190°). The consumption of the reagent depends upon the structure of the compounds. The molar ratio of the compound with reagent in case of acridines is 1 : 2, fluoranthene, pyrene, chrysene and picene 1 : 6, retene 1 : 10, and 2-methylanthracene 1 : 12. Due to bond length variation the maximum charge

density in fluoranthene, pyrene, chrysene and picene was found at positions 4 and 3, 3 and 10, 1 and 2, and 11 and 12 respectively. The presence of methyl group at positions-1 and isopropyl group at position-7 in retene hinders position-3 and -4 for oxidation and gives the corresponding 1,7-dicarboxylic acid. In other reactions where position-1 and -7 are found to be free it gives corresponding 3,4-quinone derivatives. Different time intervals were needed for reactions of different compounds (Table 1). Addition of sulphuric acid is recommended for maintaining maximum redox potential of Fe^{III} solution. The presence of zinc sulphate has catalytic effect due to slow oxidation and inaccurate results are obtained in its absence. Zinc sulphate reacts with $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ and forms zinc potassium ferricyanide which accelerates the reaction. Presence of glacial acetic acid increases solubility of the compounds and avoids precipitation. The best recovery of the sample was obtained at $48^\circ-50^\circ$. Heating beyond 75° resulted

TABLE 1—MILLIGRAM DETERMINATION OF SOME POLYNUCLEAR AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS OF ANTHRACENE OIL FRACTION OF COAL TAR*

Compd	Reaction time min	Amount taken mg	Amount obtained mg	Mole- cularity	Error %	SD (mg)	CV (%)
Fluoranthene	20	3.00	2.98	6	-0.67	0.005 8	0.195
Pyrene	20	3.00	2.98	6	-0.67	0.005 8	0.195
Chrysene	25	5.00	4.97	6	-0.60	0.010 0	0.200
Picene	25	3.00	2.98	6	-0.67	0.005 8	0.195
Retene	30	5.00	4.98	10	-0.40	0.005 8	0.116
2-Methyl anthracene	30	3.00	2.98	12	-0.67	0.005 8	0.196
Acridine	25	5.00	4.98	2	-0.40	0.005 8	0.116
2-Nitroacridine	25	3.00	2.98	2	-0.67	0.005 8	0.195
4-Nitroacridine	25	5.00	4.97	2	-0.60	0.005 8	0.116

*Average of nine determination.

in the decomposition of the reagent and at lower temperature the reactions is found to be incomplete. Although the results are given between 3 and 5 mg, the determinations are possible from 1 to 10 mg without loss of accuracy. Easily oxidisable compounds like thioureas, alcohols, phenols, carbohydrates and aromatic amines, if present, interfere in the determination by giving higher recovery.

Experimental

Aqueous $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ (0.1 N), KI (10%), H_2SO_4 (10 M), $ZnSO_4$ (3%) and starch solution (2%) were prepared. Stock solutions of fluoranthene, pyrene, chrysene, picene, retene, methylanthracene, acridine, 2-nitroacridine and 4-nitroacridine were prepared by dissolving 50–100 mg of the sample in glacial acetic acid (100 ml). All the reagents and samples were either of AnalaR grade or purified by crystallisation and determination of constant m.p.

To aliquots containing 1–5 mg of the sample were added to 0.1 N $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ (10 ml) followed by 10 M H_2SO_4 (10 ml), glacial acetic acid (10

ml) and 1% zinc sulphate solution (5 ml). The reaction mixture was then shaken gently and kept in a thermostat (48°) for 30 min. It was then cooled to room temperature and 10% KI solution (10 ml) was added. The unconsumed Fe^{III} -reagent was back-titrated with 0.1 N sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. A blank experiment was also run under identical conditions.

References

1. G. LUNGE, "Coal-tar and Ammonia", 5th. ed., Gurney and Jackson, London, 1916, Vol. II, Chap. 7; A. NASTIUKOFF, *J. Russ. Chem. Phys. Soc.*, 1904, **36**, 881; 1910, **42**, 1596; V. F. HERR, *Chem. Zeit.*, 1910, **34**, 891; E. SCHULEK and K. BURGER, *Talanta*, 1958, **1**, 147; R. E. MERRIFIELD and W. D. PHILLIPS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 2778.
2. J. LAM and A. BERG, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1965, **20**, 168; N. Z. ZANDER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1967, **226**, 257; I. HERNYOK, *Proc. Conf. Appl. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **1**, 39; R. I. PERSONOV and T. A. TEPHITASKAYA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1965, **20**, 1125.
3. A. BERKA, J. VULTERIN and J. ZYKS, "Newer Redox Titrants", Pergamon, London, 1965, p. 20; M. N. KRISHNA, G. PRASAD and U. R. K. RAMA, *Microchim Acta*, 1978, **2**, 89.